

Table 2

SNP	chr	Pos	EA/OA	SNP-exposure			SNP-outcome		
				beta	SE	p	beta	SE	p
rs10010325	4	106106353	A/C	0.022	0.001	1.50E-63	-0.045	0.051	0.378
rs10011137	4	56498199	G/A	0.009	0.001	1.40E-11	0.007	0.053	0.896
rs10031777	4	48498290	C/T	0.013	0.001	9.90E-23	-0.05	0.05	0.323
rs1004982	15	51613811	C/T	-0.013	0.001	1.20E-20	-0.062	0.058	0.29
rs10059884	5	32832474	A/C	-0.027	0.001	9.30E-94	0.015	0.051	0.761
rs10061757	5	56086805	C/G	0.013	0.001	2.90E-22	-0.037	0.052	0.476
rs10082476	10	124164654	G/A	-0.019	0.002	2.00E-34	0.039	0.074	0.595
rs10098103	8	23397081	C/T	-0.01	0.002	3.20E-11	0.062	0.058	0.282
rs10105330	8	58136501	T/C	0.015	0.002	2.90E-11	-0.144	0.094	0.125
rs10114341	9	96919182	C/T	0.009	0.001	8.70E-11	0.046	0.051	0.364
rs10114881	9	76676071	C/T	0.008	0.001	7.90E-09	0.041	0.056	0.466
rs10123659	9	83235735	G/T	0.013	0.002	1.90E-11	0.069	0.069	0.316
rs10129429	14	92430831	A/G	-0.022	0.001	4.10E-60	0.074	0.051	0.151
rs10131337	14	37144516	T/C	0.014	0.002	5.20E-21	0.002	0.058	0.977
rs1013495	10	81140253	T/C	-0.021	0.001	5.80E-60	0.035	0.051	0.486
rs10139746	14	75040338	G/A	-0.015	0.001	9.80E-30	-0.027	0.051	0.593
rs10155941	7	134422732	C/T	-0.012	0.001	5.90E-19	-0.005	0.05	0.926
rs10165255	2	10199601	G/A	-0.016	0.001	1.10E-35	0.007	0.056	0.903
rs10181220	2	20035567	T/C	-0.008	0.001	1.80E-10	0.057	0.051	0.26
rs1020048	9	86666993	C/A	-0.017	0.002	3.90E-25	0.055	0.067	0.411
rs10202701	2	232328681	T/C	0.019	0.001	2.20E-46	-0.062	0.05	0.216
rs10207736	2	217863554	T/A	0.013	0.001	2.10E-19	0.071	0.053	0.179
rs10221274	17	68093498	T/G	-0.012	0.001	6.40E-18	-0.046	0.051	0.367
rs10233251	7	46211533	G/A	0.02	0.002	2.00E-23	-0.019	0.069	0.786
rs10241336	7	19610215	C/T	-0.015	0.001	1.50E-27	-0.027	0.055	0.624
rs10253161	7	46996392	G/A	-0.008	0.001	1.10E-08	-0.024	0.052	0.644
rs10283100	8	120596023	G/A	0.031	0.003	4.20E-28	0.02	0.097	0.84
rs10401891	19	4962848	T/C	-0.02	0.001	1.00E-46	-0.064	0.057	0.261
rs1042838	11	100933412	A/C	-0.01	0.002	1.30E-08	0.094	0.069	0.175
rs1043413	19	41939297	G/C	0.019	0.001	5.00E-46	-0.028	0.052	0.598
rs1043547	14	93406789	T/G	-0.012	0.002	7.50E-15	-0.084	0.062	0.179
rs1044299	1	176811873	T/C	0.021	0.001	8.00E-61	-0.083	0.05	0.102
rs10498672	6	7797840	G/C	0.02	0.002	3.30E-32	0.01	0.061	0.865
rs1050969	8	103661730	C/T	0.031	0.005	1.50E-09	0.193	0.234	0.411
rs1051547	16	19279380	C/T	-0.01	0.001	5.20E-13	-0.058	0.051	0.253
rs1052256	1	172363488	G/A	0.019	0.002	1.70E-31	0.143	0.062	0.021
rs1056173	7	5364041	A/G	-0.018	0.002	1.60E-17	-0.056	0.086	0.517
rs1065368	16	1036860	C/T	0.013	0.001	3.00E-21	0.023	0.051	0.644
rs1074683	20	32304653	G/C	-0.03	0.001	2.80E-90	0.007	0.06	0.907
rs10748128	12	69827658	T/G	0.026	0.001	9.50E-79	0.084	0.053	0.112
rs10756792	9	16726119	T/C	0.013	0.002	3.50E-19	0.037	0.06	0.544
rs10770705	12	20857467	C/A	-0.015	0.001	2.70E-28	-0.014	0.055	0.803
rs10773083	12	124791650	T/G	-0.017	0.001	2.30E-33	-0.049	0.051	0.329
rs10775348	16	88806348	G/A	0.019	0.001	1.40E-39	0.051	0.055	0.349
rs10789401	1	42081111	G/A	-0.01	0.001	6.90E-13	0.012	0.057	0.839
rs10826579	10	29491536	A/G	-0.014	0.002	1.20E-13	0.043	0.077	0.579
rs10831284	11	94667964	A/G	-0.012	0.002	4.10E-10	0.03	0.067	0.657
rs10832961	11	18653957	G/C	-0.016	0.002	3.70E-24	0.004	0.052	0.937
rs10840242	11	9474382	C/T	0.01	0.001	3.50E-13	0.032	0.052	0.533
rs10861678	12	107319661	A/G	-0.016	0.001	5.30E-26	-0.058	0.06	0.337
rs10874746	1	93323971	C/T	0.016	0.001	9.90E-31	0.004	0.052	0.941
rs10901216	9	133471891	A/G	-0.022	0.001	7.70E-57	0.119	0.051	0.018
rs10916606	1	224570425	T/C	0.017	0.002	1.70E-25	-0.022	0.06	0.707
rs10922478	1	89144053	G/A	0.019	0.001	7.60E-48	-0.044	0.053	0.412
rs10923724	1	119546842	T/C	0.009	0.001	4.80E-13	0.036	0.054	0.509
rs10943915	6	83617970	T/A	0.011	0.001	6.30E-14	0.019	0.055	0.727
rs10945540	6	158738975	A/G	-0.015	0.001	3.00E-27	0.026	0.052	0.611
rs10948	19	10754905	T/G	-0.017	0.001	3.00E-36	-0.069	0.056	0.218
rs10953083	7	92657034	A/C	0.01	0.001	9.10E-15	0	0.05	0.998
rs10980706	9	113803627	T/G	-0.016	0.002	9.30E-26	-0.066	0.062	0.285
rs10989088	9	98823407	A/G	0.01	0.001	1.40E-11	0.024	0.056	0.669
rs10995319	10	52762887	C/T	-0.014	0.002	1.20E-19	0.025	0.058	0.666

rs11001271	10	76822260	A/G	0.008	0.002	3.20E-08	-0.041	0.053	0.437
rs11049708	12	28697814	C/T	-0.03	0.001	2.20E-94	0.02	0.057	0.73
rs11058226	12	122938958	C/T	0.016	0.001	3.70E-27	0.003	0.064	0.96
rs11088114	21	30612396	A/C	0.013	0.002	6.50E-10	0.054	0.096	0.575
rs11122824	2	121591475	T/A	0.012	0.002	1.90E-13	0.006	0.056	0.918
rs11129108	3	23179483	C/T	0.008	0.001	2.20E-08	0.04	0.051	0.438
rs11141738	9	89910210	T/C	-0.012	0.002	8.70E-16	0.016	0.059	0.787
rs11144782	9	78795213	G/C	-0.012	0.002	7.40E-12	0.002	0.064	0.977
rs11152363	18	53057188	A/G	0.012	0.002	1.30E-11	-0.012	0.063	0.855
rs11167487	5	149301335	C/T	0.012	0.002	6.50E-12	0.046	0.071	0.521
rs111738917	4	106240476	A/G	-0.029	0.004	1.70E-12	-0.288	0.386	0.456
rs11196169	10	114721237	G/A	-0.008	0.001	4.40E-09	0.084	0.051	0.102
rs11198898	10	121118492	C/A	-0.02	0.002	2.10E-39	-0.008	0.066	0.908
rs11205303	1	149906413	C/T	0.034	0.001	5.00E-149	-0.044	0.054	0.418
rs11209173	1	68369950	A/G	-0.008	0.001	1.30E-08	0.12	0.061	0.049
rs112153300	21	47547474	A/G	0.024	0.002	2.30E-25	0.188	0.09	0.036
rs11217863	11	120293138	A/G	-0.022	0.002	1.30E-27	0.105	0.076	0.164
rs11221158	11	127980209	T/C	-0.012	0.002	1.40E-14	-0.01	0.059	0.872
rs11245333	10	126383088	A/C	0.015	0.001	7.10E-31	-0.013	0.05	0.8
rs112471207	2	172415930	T/C	-0.016	0.002	6.50E-26	-0.005	0.064	0.943
rs11252860	10	5024356	C/A	0.014	0.002	1.90E-19	-0.007	0.063	0.908
rs11259936	15	84580582	C/A	0.036	0.001	1.00E-164	0.028	0.05	0.572
rs112635811	11	1930713	T/C	-0.014	0.002	5.70E-09	0.095	0.096	0.322
rs113595815	15	86071450	G/T	-0.02	0.003	8.40E-12	0.042	0.123	0.73
rs113851505	16	341988	T/C	-0.009	0.002	4.70E-08	-0.013	0.069	0.856
rs11466399	1	218591623	A/G	0.028	0.001	3.30E-82	-0.018	0.053	0.74
rs114784809	5	127674221	A/G	0.031	0.004	7.00E-14	-0.19	0.192	0.321
rs11553764	12	104415244	T/C	0.012	0.002	8.00E-13	0.006	0.072	0.936
rs11671106	19	46367025	T/C	-0.008	0.001	1.50E-09	0.003	0.057	0.958
rs11681299	2	88901732	T/C	0.022	0.001	2.10E-55	0.015	0.053	0.775
rs116893322	15	85524628	A/G	0.016	0.002	5.30E-19	0.054	0.064	0.397
rs11690176	2	242356887	A/G	-0.011	0.001	1.30E-15	0.009	0.056	0.878
rs1169738	12	121584410	A/G	0.022	0.004	6.10E-09	-0.039	0.137	0.776
rs11708067	3	123065778	G/A	-0.013	0.002	7.30E-19	0.093	0.067	0.161
rs11708810	3	55500045	A/T	0.014	0.002	2.40E-21	-0.027	0.064	0.669
rs11710894	3	112991959	T/C	-0.012	0.002	3.30E-12	0.055	0.056	0.325
rs11711770	3	43066768	G/A	-0.014	0.002	1.80E-16	0.077	0.068	0.258
rs11713042	3	41288004	C/T	0.012	0.001	2.40E-21	-0.054	0.051	0.284
rs1171614	10	61469538	C/T	-0.019	0.002	3.20E-33	0.046	0.069	0.499
rs11720869	3	185619716	A/G	0.009	0.001	9.40E-12	-0.016	0.051	0.749
rs11722554	4	5016883	A/G	-0.032	0.003	8.10E-21	0.132	0.1	0.188
rs11741562	5	79893662	G/T	0.008	0.001	2.20E-08	0.103	0.054	0.058
rs11743919	5	156754251	T/C	-0.011	0.002	1.00E-12	0.052	0.063	0.409
rs11746047	5	123997308	T/C	0.011	0.001	1.60E-17	-0.004	0.051	0.937
rs11747997	5	142790752	C/A	0.012	0.001	1.60E-16	0.059	0.055	0.287
rs11774206	8	144375815	C/T	-0.015	0.002	2.40E-23	0.013	0.069	0.845
rs11775903	8	25321076	G/A	0.009	0.001	5.70E-12	0.067	0.052	0.199
rs117793215	15	100535681	T/C	0.028	0.004	6.30E-14	0.004	0.176	0.982
rs1178172	7	18794541	C/T	0.015	0.002	8.90E-22	0.079	0.058	0.173
rs117829095	7	1932374	A/C	0.015	0.002	4.50E-10	0.077	0.078	0.329
rs11783598	8	4798388	C/T	0.008	0.001	7.80E-10	-0.037	0.051	0.468
rs1179947	12	122442444	A/G	-0.01	0.002	7.80E-10	-0.049	0.059	0.401
rs118173451	22	28356600	C/T	-0.055	0.005	9.10E-25	0.03	0.209	0.887
rs11877685	18	41880210	A/G	-0.012	0.002	3.40E-10	0.019	0.075	0.806
rs11898716	2	241828311	G/A	0.011	0.001	4.80E-14	0.053	0.057	0.35
rs11947952	4	144252964	G/C	0.009	0.001	3.20E-10	0.005	0.053	0.918
rs11955153	5	170864548	C/T	-0.023	0.002	1.70E-51	0.062	0.062	0.318
rs11957435	5	122657858	C/T	-0.012	0.002	6.40E-14	-0.131	0.061	0.031
rs11998884	9	33684436	T/C	0.019	0.003	7.50E-12	-0.061	0.092	0.506
rs12051048	16	783864	A/C	0.027	0.002	2.40E-65	-0.061	0.053	0.248
rs12055151	5	50418925	A/T	-0.009	0.001	3.90E-11	0.038	0.053	0.476
rs12126112	1	85730595	T/C	-0.009	0.002	1.20E-08	0.025	0.058	0.668
rs12130046	1	67444043	A/G	-0.017	0.002	4.00E-20	-0.068	0.06	0.262
rs12130750	1	200208417	C/T	0.009	0.001	2.00E-11	-0.07	0.05	0.164
rs12132534	1	147098986	G/C	0.011	0.002	6.20E-09	-0.001	0.091	0.992

rs12148447	15	38366667	T/C	-0.025	0.004	9.80E-11	0.008	0.154	0.958
rs12185993	3	188565410	A/T	0.01	0.002	6.30E-11	0.068	0.057	0.234
rs12209223	6	76164589	A/C	0.031	0.002	9.10E-48	-0.004	0.073	0.956
rs12342779	9	119122437	G/T	-0.031	0.002	5.10E-80	0.008	0.06	0.895
rs12348423	9	4740251	C/A	-0.013	0.002	2.90E-18	0.061	0.06	0.308
rs12362444	11	45278317	A/G	-0.009	0.001	9.10E-11	0.067	0.051	0.184
rs12406530	1	113117213	G/A	-0.016	0.002	1.10E-24	0.024	0.054	0.65
rs12452505	17	63556402	G/C	-0.03	0.002	9.90E-57	0.08	0.083	0.335
rs12452590	17	60720058	G/T	0.013	0.001	6.20E-21	-0.099	0.051	0.052
rs12459155	19	4774475	G/C	-0.014	0.002	4.10E-12	0.002	0.08	0.98
rs12466227	2	60148940	G/A	-0.01	0.001	4.60E-15	-0.024	0.054	0.654
rs12478285	2	109051753	A/G	0.008	0.001	1.00E-09	-0.051	0.05	0.313
rs12483653	21	17355049	T/C	-0.013	0.002	9.00E-16	0.059	0.06	0.326
rs12497944	3	24044111	A/G	-0.011	0.002	2.70E-13	0.035	0.057	0.546
rs12517974	5	137744369	C/A	0.01	0.002	5.10E-09	-0.074	0.062	0.231
rs12552167	9	139322927	T/C	0.018	0.001	6.20E-34	0.001	0.058	0.993
rs12584892	13	73624534	T/C	-0.013	0.002	3.30E-14	0.025	0.074	0.734
rs12592845	15	48684958	T/C	-0.025	0.002	3.30E-28	-0.028	0.076	0.707
rs12622270	2	164449314	C/T	-0.01	0.002	2.20E-09	-0.074	0.06	0.217
rs12645070	4	57770106	A/G	0.024	0.002	4.90E-47	0.015	0.059	0.797
rs12648093	4	123838758	G/A	-0.014	0.001	9.80E-20	-0.014	0.062	0.816
rs12668269	7	65779510	T/A	0.01	0.001	7.40E-12	0.023	0.057	0.691
rs12669267	7	73304636	T/C	-0.018	0.002	1.30E-19	0.009	0.072	0.901
rs12868316	13	113878523	T/C	0.009	0.002	3.20E-09	0.057	0.056	0.309
rs12903939	15	101641034	A/G	-0.011	0.002	1.70E-12	-0.008	0.062	0.895
rs1291066	20	35790918	C/G	0.016	0.002	3.50E-21	-0.016	0.055	0.775
rs12924101	16	89862906	C/A	-0.013	0.002	1.90E-15	0.14	0.079	0.077
rs12952981	17	79409189	A/G	0.012	0.001	3.00E-19	-0.015	0.052	0.778
rs12966785	18	22858941	A/G	-0.012	0.001	9.70E-18	-0.005	0.053	0.928
rs12968652	18	46501070	A/G	-0.014	0.001	1.50E-25	-0.094	0.054	0.082
rs12982509	19	3412057	C/T	0.018	0.002	1.90E-30	-0.078	0.059	0.19
rs12985850	19	2155042	A/G	0.025	0.001	2.30E-77	0	0.053	0.994
rs13014796	2	200321050	A/G	-0.017	0.002	8.60E-23	-0.072	0.072	0.321
rs13168903	5	158517233	G/T	-0.008	0.001	1.50E-09	-0.027	0.051	0.6
rs1317867	17	21276114	G/A	0.019	0.001	6.60E-45	-0.027	0.05	0.597
rs13178887	5	88355993	C/T	-0.02	0.001	1.30E-50	0.069	0.055	0.205
rs13179048	5	95542726	A/C	0.012	0.001	5.50E-18	0.041	0.053	0.438
rs13226864	7	100499315	A/G	0.012	0.002	4.60E-12	0.031	0.061	0.616
rs13251736	8	32291790	C/T	-0.018	0.003	9.10E-10	-0.115	0.156	0.462
rs13334364	16	67332365	C/T	-0.025	0.002	1.90E-24	0.11	0.075	0.142
rs13340461	6	41924278	T/C	0.018	0.001	5.20E-35	-0.002	0.057	0.974
rs13406427	2	46878351	G/C	0.012	0.001	2.60E-15	0.081	0.06	0.175
rs13412980	2	1545231	A/C	-0.01	0.002	7.00E-09	-0.077	0.058	0.183
rs1352982	10	25332461	G/A	0.01	0.001	1.10E-13	-0.094	0.051	0.068
rs1353778	3	134088443	T/A	-0.009	0.001	2.00E-10	-0.007	0.051	0.894
rs136029	22	46236425	A/G	0.012	0.001	4.00E-19	0.015	0.05	0.764
rs138198562	12	46429309	C/T	0.022	0.003	2.90E-12	-0.208	0.14	0.136
rs138548025	4	135114664	C/T	0.019	0.003	4.60E-09	0.05	0.133	0.71
rs138937927	16	51095561	T/C	-0.045	0.004	1.70E-25	-0.166	0.143	0.248
rs1393421	15	38369210	A/G	0.016	0.003	3.20E-09	-0.036	0.104	0.728
rs1395602	16	4911239	C/A	0.01	0.001	7.90E-14	-0.084	0.05	0.094
rs140182288	1	2226159	T/C	0.023	0.004	2.40E-08	0.207	0.152	0.174
rs140753094	1	40641118	A/C	0.015	0.002	3.40E-14	0	0.065	0.997
rs1415701	6	130345835	A/G	-0.031	0.001	5.60E-100	-0.031	0.058	0.591
rs1420150	7	33321872	G/C	-0.01	0.002	1.50E-09	0.027	0.055	0.623
rs142190120	2	219953832	T/C	-0.046	0.006	2.70E-15	0.042	0.477	0.93
rs143384	20	34025756	G/A	0.059	0.001	1.00E-200	0.005	0.051	0.917
rs143840904	11	2813322	T/C	-0.103	0.005	1.20E-100	0.448	0.317	0.158
rs144351518	4	1893651	G/A	-0.036	0.004	1.20E-21	0.156	0.178	0.38
rs1443536	4	82174165	G/A	0.032	0.001	2.30E-112	-0.04	0.052	0.436
rs1443749	7	121960438	T/C	0.012	0.001	2.50E-18	0.045	0.051	0.38
rs145873050	1	150766213	T/G	-0.026	0.004	2.60E-10	0.059	0.149	0.693
rs146381464	3	51463177	A/C	0.08	0.004	4.10E-74	-0.134	0.205	0.513
rs1468177	22	30544559	C/T	0.011	0.001	5.70E-15	0.037	0.051	0.471
rs146851424	13	50377910	C/A	0.094	0.005	3.70E-95	-0.296	0.188	0.114

rs147110934	19	55993436	T/G	-0.066	0.004	1.30E-54	0.32	0.333	0.337
rs147176253	16	3946485	A/G	-0.018	0.003	2.00E-11	0.156	0.103	0.13
rs1472565	1	19755030	C/T	-0.015	0.001	7.20E-31	0.074	0.05	0.143
rs1474647	1	22441865	T/C	-0.013	0.001	1.60E-24	0.051	0.051	0.317
rs147472851	14	36245495	A/G	0.013	0.002	2.00E-17	0.052	0.061	0.393
rs1490384	6	126851160	T/C	0.033	0.001	1.60E-140	0.033	0.05	0.512
rs1490819	5	67099798	T/C	0.016	0.002	7.30E-20	0.017	0.066	0.794
rs149290349	2	43451957	A/G	0.014	0.002	1.30E-08	-0.083	0.139	0.551
rs149802978	5	102346866	G/C	-0.022	0.003	8.10E-14	-0.15	0.108	0.164
rs149840699	20	49210579	A/G	0.019	0.002	1.30E-14	0.179	0.098	0.066
rs150095746	8	76486799	G/A	0.023	0.004	1.30E-08	-0.231	0.174	0.184
rs151123887	20	34593288	A/G	-0.041	0.005	1.40E-18	-0.222	0.328	0.497
rs1512104	4	26021310	A/G	0.009	0.002	2.50E-08	0.117	0.056	0.038
rs151305167	2	5832142	T/C	-0.014	0.002	6.90E-11	-0.095	0.098	0.333
rs1513572	4	21850305	C/T	0.007	0.001	2.90E-08	0.023	0.051	0.656
rs1514134	1	56116513	C/T	-0.009	0.001	6.90E-12	0.035	0.051	0.493
rs1524065	7	38126589	A/C	0.016	0.001	4.50E-32	0.071	0.057	0.211
rs1531851	2	20694122	C/T	-0.008	0.001	2.00E-08	-0.022	0.057	0.708
rs1545552	2	33360338	G/A	0.024	0.001	2.40E-61	0.079	0.059	0.181
rs1563387	8	121179924	T/G	-0.008	0.001	1.10E-09	0.083	0.053	0.117
rs1569364	8	116629732	T/C	-0.011	0.001	1.00E-17	-0.048	0.054	0.369
rs1573891	15	99186488	C/G	-0.034	0.002	3.40E-79	-0.013	0.097	0.89
rs1574220	5	314518	C/T	0.022	0.002	7.40E-20	-0.192	0.132	0.145
rs1593071	5	42786309	C/A	-0.018	0.001	8.90E-44	0.046	0.052	0.378
rs1599473	8	120475358	T/G	-0.02	0.002	4.60E-39	-0.137	0.061	0.025
rs1624841	18	7556208	T/C	0.01	0.002	8.30E-10	-0.02	0.073	0.784
rs1679910	1	53582321	A/G	0.009	0.001	8.20E-12	0.004	0.051	0.942
rs16824590	2	203137347	A/G	-0.016	0.002	9.10E-15	0.048	0.077	0.537
rs16928433	12	1546814	A/G	-0.014	0.002	5.10E-11	-0.089	0.083	0.284
rs16942323	15	89383764	C/T	-0.093	0.004	4.70E-116	-0.011	0.236	0.961
rs17034560	1	10229158	A/G	0.02	0.003	6.30E-09	-0.05	0.131	0.7
rs17038164	1	118862669	C/T	-0.031	0.001	6.50E-95	-0.046	0.059	0.434
rs17038954	2	1645673	T/C	0.02	0.003	1.20E-13	0.126	0.112	0.26
rs17148514	11	85526399	T/C	-0.014	0.002	1.10E-18	0.144	0.067	0.031
rs17157112	7	28779946	G/T	-0.016	0.001	5.50E-35	-0.087	0.05	0.083
rs17197114	14	21894526	C/T	0.016	0.002	5.90E-20	0.066	0.069	0.343
rs17236066	2	174863486	A/G	0.018	0.002	2.90E-13	-0.145	0.087	0.095
rs1729090	8	13107258	T/C	-0.01	0.001	4.10E-13	0.033	0.051	0.52
rs1730040	3	158030962	G/A	0.016	0.001	5.10E-32	-0.044	0.05	0.379
rs17357954	1	41487337	T/G	0.03	0.002	2.10E-84	-0.109	0.06	0.069
rs17400325	2	178565913	C/T	0.04	0.003	3.30E-35	-0.237	0.178	0.183
rs17409588	5	31528627	C/T	0.01	0.001	3.90E-13	-0.001	0.055	0.985
rs1741344	20	4101800	T/C	-0.02	0.001	2.40E-49	0.085	0.053	0.108
rs174529	11	61543961	C/T	-0.009	0.001	6.10E-12	0.03	0.051	0.555
rs17454369	4	87666334	C/G	0.019	0.003	8.10E-12	-0.145	0.192	0.45
rs17472816	10	12020794	G/A	-0.024	0.003	1.80E-16	0.101	0.113	0.372
rs17511102	2	37960613	T/A	0.032	0.002	3.40E-45	-0.233	0.098	0.017
rs17592880	11	59286521	G/A	-0.019	0.003	2.00E-09	-0.022	0.092	0.809
rs17599450	19	30328753	T/C	0.009	0.001	1.30E-10	0.057	0.053	0.274
rs17741562	2	148563066	C/T	0.01	0.002	3.70E-09	0.029	0.08	0.719
rs17800727	16	53481010	G/A	0.021	0.001	5.10E-48	0.014	0.057	0.81
rs17855988	7	73474825	C/G	0.019	0.002	1.20E-17	0.136	0.112	0.227
rs184090834	2	219873482	A/T	-0.087	0.006	4.00E-52	0.646	0.32	0.043
rs1863758	15	56151030	G/A	0.008	0.001	1.10E-08	0.029	0.052	0.577
rs1867780	15	77407114	G/C	-0.015	0.001	4.70E-24	-0.098	0.056	0.077
rs1884897	20	6612832	G/A	-0.035	0.001	4.60E-142	0.033	0.054	0.542
rs188571030	15	75786845	T/C	0.047	0.007	2.30E-11	0.78	0.427	0.068
rs1889643	6	141721197	A/C	-0.01	0.001	7.80E-11	0.033	0.057	0.562
rs1910252	8	49407362	T/C	0.017	0.002	2.40E-21	-0.014	0.072	0.844
rs1948047	6	47585912	C/T	0.011	0.001	3.10E-15	0.063	0.062	0.311
rs1952256	1	184035116	G/A	0.033	0.001	3.20E-127	-0.011	0.051	0.83
rs1961247	11	32949014	T/C	0.008	0.001	1.30E-09	-0.01	0.052	0.847
rs1962482	1	86313536	T/G	-0.012	0.002	1.70E-12	0.016	0.078	0.833
rs1984119	9	98368761	C/T	-0.03	0.002	2.30E-84	-0.049	0.056	0.381
rs1985278	1	21091861	T/G	-0.015	0.001	5.40E-30	0.122	0.052	0.019

rs1985299	3	183538416	G/A	0.009	0.001	1.90E-11	-0.045	0.051	0.374
rs1996711	3	146980646	C/T	-0.012	0.001	1.60E-20	-0.027	0.05	0.594
rs2006122	17	61987405	T/A	0.037	0.001	4.80E-141	-0.033	0.06	0.579
rs2016437	1	235539355	G/T	0.009	0.001	2.50E-12	-0.043	0.054	0.427
rs2034395	2	121610186	T/G	-0.023	0.002	2.50E-41	-0.118	0.069	0.089
rs2035901	4	145521867	G/A	0.024	0.001	7.00E-75	-0.013	0.051	0.803
rs2065036	22	28099361	T/C	-0.009	0.001	1.20E-11	0.018	0.051	0.722
rs2072346	16	4027423	T/C	0.016	0.002	4.50E-21	-0.012	0.062	0.843
rs2093210	14	60957279	T/C	-0.029	0.001	5.20E-103	0.009	0.055	0.872
rs2099333	19	19605963	T/C	-0.02	0.002	9.30E-31	0.137	0.07	0.051
rs2110748	2	202345476	A/C	-0.031	0.004	1.40E-12	-0.072	0.202	0.723
rs2131371	12	46796522	C/A	0.015	0.001	8.80E-26	0.039	0.053	0.466
rs2138628	9	108931732	A/T	-0.016	0.001	5.40E-30	0.065	0.053	0.223
rs215226	12	591300	G/A	0.019	0.001	1.80E-45	0.013	0.052	0.799
rs2157323	6	116729779	C/T	0.015	0.001	1.30E-23	0.001	0.057	0.992
rs2181834	10	102661251	T/G	0.016	0.001	3.10E-33	-0.136	0.051	0.007
rs219162	2	33219099	G/C	0.01	0.001	4.30E-12	0.017	0.052	0.739
rs2194411	3	185548663	A/G	0.043	0.002	1.40E-107	0.019	0.073	0.798
rs2219320	1	26803430	C/T	-0.018	0.001	3.70E-34	0.038	0.062	0.542
rs2229094	6	31540556	C/T	-0.024	0.001	3.90E-59	-0.053	0.061	0.387
rs2239748	13	33101817	T/C	0.014	0.001	5.90E-25	-0.039	0.051	0.447
rs2240169	19	1018830	T/C	0.009	0.001	4.50E-10	-0.002	0.052	0.964
rs2270894	3	9975386	G/C	-0.027	0.002	2.10E-59	0.014	0.057	0.803
rs227745	17	54762165	A/T	0.019	0.001	1.60E-39	-0.06	0.053	0.255
rs228279	17	36918350	C/T	-0.016	0.002	1.30E-24	-0.177	0.063	0.005
rs2290154	18	77211175	C/T	-0.015	0.001	1.80E-28	0.001	0.052	0.986
rs2302580	4	8608634	T/C	-0.017	0.001	1.50E-38	0.03	0.051	0.55
rs2303597	2	71780821	C/T	-0.013	0.001	1.30E-20	0.046	0.055	0.404
rs2305141	2	233684402	G/A	0.014	0.001	8.90E-25	-0.015	0.057	0.79
rs2326181	20	3312596	T/C	-0.009	0.001	5.50E-11	0	0.05	0.995
rs235763	20	6705246	C/T	-0.016	0.001	1.50E-32	0.057	0.052	0.272
rs2368274	10	28193276	T/G	-0.013	0.002	1.30E-08	-0.073	0.075	0.331
rs2378788	1	183918161	G/A	-0.009	0.001	4.80E-09	-0.012	0.055	0.824
rs2380893	2	141585138	G/A	0.007	0.001	1.20E-08	-0.084	0.05	0.097
rs2410728	5	86340997	G/C	0.011	0.002	5.30E-13	0.021	0.054	0.697
rs2413141	22	33051198	G/A	-0.02	0.002	6.10E-28	0.071	0.072	0.325
rs2427312	20	60970591	T/C	-0.011	0.002	6.70E-12	-0.098	0.077	0.204
rs244711	5	176509193	T/C	0.039	0.002	3.60E-148	-0.032	0.055	0.558
rs246185	16	14395432	C/T	0.018	0.001	2.70E-37	-0.015	0.052	0.772
rs2475314	10	121644781	A/G	-0.011	0.001	4.50E-16	-0.026	0.051	0.603
rs2503716	1	2149292	T/C	0.012	0.001	9.20E-19	-0.011	0.052	0.833
rs2513299	11	68410157	T/C	0.022	0.002	1.00E-33	-0.086	0.088	0.332
rs2527166	8	5532881	T/C	-0.009	0.002	1.20E-08	0.1	0.063	0.112
rs2545101	5	180646014	T/C	-0.011	0.002	6.30E-12	-0.065	0.06	0.279
rs2570515	2	47297082	T/C	-0.009	0.001	4.70E-10	0.014	0.058	0.808
rs2592831	4	1711404	C/T	0.018	0.001	2.90E-37	0.007	0.051	0.894
rs2595508	2	232253390	G/A	-0.013	0.002	8.00E-17	0.076	0.055	0.167
rs2610986	4	18037231	T/C	-0.021	0.001	8.90E-50	-0.047	0.053	0.378
rs2613946	3	112825573	G/A	0.011	0.001	2.20E-16	0.018	0.05	0.725
rs261532	5	138949362	T/G	0.015	0.001	1.90E-25	-0.023	0.061	0.705
rs264766	5	64388979	C/T	0.013	0.001	5.30E-21	-0.031	0.054	0.567
rs2648725	10	93015079	A/T	0.021	0.002	2.90E-40	0.022	0.066	0.742
rs2654969	15	99532777	G/A	-0.014	0.002	3.70E-19	-0.067	0.061	0.266
rs2663335	17	929741	T/A	-0.01	0.002	6.60E-09	0.005	0.055	0.925
rs2675228	3	13553380	T/C	-0.027	0.002	6.70E-35	0.023	0.092	0.8
rs2697546	5	90321288	G/A	-0.009	0.001	8.10E-11	0.007	0.053	0.901
rs2715094	7	50730452	A/G	-0.012	0.002	4.30E-15	0.013	0.052	0.808
rs2715553	17	38496320	A/G	0.015	0.001	1.50E-28	-0.094	0.051	0.062
rs2724616	12	11870768	G/A	-0.021	0.001	2.20E-52	0.038	0.052	0.46
rs2732744	7	84842884	C/T	-0.01	0.002	4.50E-10	0.047	0.059	0.424
rs273974	7	137614713	T/C	0.013	0.001	4.80E-22	-0.022	0.05	0.663
rs2741311	2	233239743	C/T	-0.029	0.002	1.50E-32	-0.005	0.083	0.952
rs2746026	17	18134354	T/C	0.012	0.001	5.80E-19	0.024	0.052	0.639
rs274668	5	6711630	T/C	-0.011	0.001	2.40E-15	0.032	0.052	0.542
rs2755237	13	41109429	C/A	-0.014	0.002	1.40E-14	-0.039	0.082	0.63

rs2763263	6	168814392	A/T	-0.021	0.002	4.80E-45	-0.022	0.053	0.677
rs2780226	6	34199092	T/C	-0.063	0.002	5.30E-168	-0.246	0.112	0.028
rs2789514	9	129833029	A/G	0.017	0.002	8.40E-19	0.032	0.111	0.774
rs2793007	9	125664882	C/G	-0.014	0.002	3.40E-14	-0.076	0.066	0.252
rs2808290	10	27900882	T/C	0.014	0.001	1.40E-27	0.02	0.051	0.696
rs2812237	13	51299120	A/G	-0.018	0.002	8.50E-24	-0.098	0.067	0.143
rs2835676	21	38591311	T/C	0.009	0.001	2.30E-11	-0.017	0.052	0.738
rs28481863	12	123902361	A/G	-0.027	0.002	1.70E-59	0.058	0.065	0.367
rs28503877	4	166319470	G/C	0.01	0.001	8.00E-11	-0.049	0.058	0.399
rs285187	20	42316582	A/G	-0.014	0.002	1.10E-12	0.063	0.089	0.477
rs28519617	3	135874930	G/T	-0.023	0.001	1.80E-56	0.106	0.062	0.086
rs28576486	19	7213287	A/G	-0.012	0.001	2.60E-19	0.015	0.051	0.773
rs28625289	4	120523005	T/A	-0.01	0.002	1.60E-08	-0.098	0.058	0.094
rs28682325	2	54700447	C/T	0.025	0.003	9.80E-15	0.092	0.222	0.68
rs28701981	9	98217581	C/T	0.03	0.001	7.19E-107	0.07	0.052	0.176
rs2871960	3	141121814	C/A	0.057	0.001	1.00E-200	-0.101	0.05	0.044
rs28757157	15	51545401	T/C	-0.04	0.003	9.60E-35	-0.023	0.097	0.81
rs28929474	14	94844947	T/C	0.101	0.005	1.50E-102	0.707	0.189	0
rs2925155	8	75886297	T/C	-0.019	0.002	5.70E-35	0.058	0.056	0.301
rs3020407	6	152307261	A/G	-0.012	0.001	2.10E-17	-0.011	0.054	0.834
rs3020644	6	31894626	G/A	-0.024	0.001	2.60E-69	0.111	0.052	0.034
rs310796	12	77453226	T/G	0.015	0.001	7.80E-27	-0.032	0.057	0.581
rs3116168	2	232989831	C/T	0.028	0.001	7.50E-83	0.058	0.061	0.341
rs3118906	13	51106788	A/G	-0.038	0.001	6.40E-152	0.01	0.054	0.853
rs332194	10	28922228	C/T	-0.017	0.002	1.70E-24	-0.028	0.065	0.671
rs34074573	14	23789955	G/A	0.022	0.002	2.60E-36	-0.037	0.074	0.618
rs34118426	12	94201279	G/A	-0.021	0.001	5.90E-50	-0.009	0.055	0.876
rs34454426	3	87346735	A/G	-0.02	0.003	2.00E-11	0.1	0.098	0.304
rs34517439	1	78450517	A/C	0.031	0.002	7.10E-55	0.051	0.075	0.501
rs34544557	11	69911825	T/C	-0.012	0.001	2.70E-19	-0.003	0.05	0.947
rs34587452	4	1009900	C/G	-0.019	0.002	7.90E-34	-0.036	0.063	0.572
rs34751492	2	227268646	C/T	-0.018	0.003	2.80E-08	0.134	0.138	0.332
rs34773647	1	150130983	T/G	0.046	0.005	1.00E-23	0.024	0.071	0.731
rs34776209	7	23513093	T/C	-0.027	0.002	1.50E-71	0.016	0.062	0.794
rs34831515	19	17275777	T/C	-0.018	0.002	2.90E-32	-0.036	0.054	0.503
rs34849253	18	33024107	A/G	0.013	0.001	1.70E-18	-0.105	0.055	0.056
rs34958982	11	47547046	C/T	-0.021	0.001	8.60E-53	-0.051	0.054	0.341
rs34970912	16	73068163	G/C	0.027	0.004	1.10E-13	-0.07	0.19	0.714
rs35130225	5	112116069	A/G	-0.011	0.001	1.90E-18	0.038	0.05	0.455
rs351373	1	212426631	T/G	-0.009	0.001	2.80E-12	0.043	0.057	0.449
rs35307904	9	78511889	A/G	-0.04	0.002	1.00E-88	0.008	0.069	0.906
rs35348430	10	96100627	G/A	-0.011	0.002	1.40E-09	0.004	0.069	0.949
rs35628589	20	61440005	T/C	0.034	0.003	3.90E-36	-0.096	0.09	0.283
rs35665085	22	17625915	A/G	-0.018	0.003	4.50E-10	-0.032	0.111	0.773
rs35756741	12	12868701	T/C	-0.026	0.002	4.60E-30	-0.116	0.083	0.164
rs35874463	15	67457698	G/A	0.056	0.003	3.70E-88	-0.034	0.128	0.791
rs35917062	2	191660828	A/G	-0.017	0.002	1.50E-16	0.003	0.103	0.978
rs35954730	10	12943111	A/G	-0.022	0.001	8.70E-51	0.07	0.06	0.242
rs35990522	9	119274481	A/T	0.026	0.002	1.60E-25	0.223	0.149	0.135
rs36226649	14	24835500	C/T	0.037	0.003	2.50E-45	-0.003	0.117	0.983
rs3751877	16	15154898	C/T	-0.014	0.002	9.90E-11	-0.023	0.076	0.765
rs3751921	17	25642315	G/A	0.008	0.001	1.60E-10	-0.031	0.052	0.552
rs3756668	5	67596088	A/G	-0.013	0.001	8.30E-23	0.015	0.051	0.775
rs3795949	2	23926932	A/C	0.019	0.001	7.70E-51	-0.028	0.05	0.577
rs37978	7	8017851	G/A	0.015	0.001	2.30E-31	0.004	0.051	0.942
rs3807945	7	20415826	A/G	0.02	0.001	4.10E-52	-0.005	0.051	0.924
rs3821156	2	36741530	G/A	-0.013	0.001	1.70E-23	-0.007	0.051	0.896
rs3866205	4	124089399	T/A	0.012	0.002	2.90E-10	-0.105	0.088	0.231
rs3925	8	38281658	A/G	-0.01	0.002	2.40E-10	0.026	0.065	0.697
rs41271299	6	19839415	T/C	0.089	0.003	1.20E-200	-0.168	0.199	0.397
rs42039	7	92244422	T/C	0.045	0.002	2.10E-194	-0.041	0.059	0.488
rs4239436	18	20731930	G/A	0.05	0.002	1.00E-200	0.075	0.06	0.212
rs4252548	19	55879672	T/C	-0.067	0.004	7.60E-51	-0.159	0.159	0.319
rs4287972	4	88645798	T/C	-0.013	0.001	5.20E-22	-0.034	0.05	0.495
rs4291276	8	23173591	G/A	-0.019	0.002	5.50E-36	-0.048	0.063	0.439

rs4293126	11	122804133	A/G	0.013	0.001	9.40E-22	0.007	0.05	0.891
rs4339935	10	4986044	T/G	-0.008	0.001	4.10E-10	0.009	0.051	0.865
rs4361209	22	39281636	G/A	0.014	0.002	1.60E-18	0.066	0.061	0.282
rs437853	2	196973	C/T	0.015	0.002	3.60E-15	-0.059	0.065	0.366
rs4401680	6	140164286	G/T	0.01	0.002	4.80E-11	-0.153	0.062	0.014
rs4415953	14	80943372	A/G	0.009	0.001	3.60E-10	-0.042	0.052	0.42
rs4421120	5	32763118	A/G	0.025	0.002	2.30E-46	-0.037	0.077	0.634
rs4510865	8	12685204	T/A	-0.011	0.002	9.20E-12	0.095	0.072	0.188
rs4541010	15	62207619	C/T	0.011	0.001	3.60E-16	-0.02	0.055	0.717
rs45446698	7	99332948	G/T	0.033	0.003	1.80E-24	-0.067	0.112	0.551
rs4545829	16	80005642	A/G	0.008	0.001	2.90E-09	-0.05	0.05	0.318
rs45474992	19	47724564	T/C	-0.025	0.004	8.40E-13	0.036	0.137	0.791
rs45478299	7	87111321	A/G	0.011	0.002	2.70E-10	0.056	0.063	0.377
rs45601237	1	31196255	A/G	0.008	0.001	3.20E-08	-0.02	0.056	0.718
rs4630854	21	47437220	G/A	0.008	0.001	7.60E-09	-0.049	0.053	0.356
rs467022	5	55805639	T/C	-0.009	0.001	1.70E-09	-0.022	0.053	0.682
rs4723399	7	35273116	C/G	-0.01	0.001	1.30E-12	-0.052	0.051	0.303
rs4735769	8	78104676	C/A	0.028	0.001	9.30E-85	-0.007	0.06	0.913
rs4756786	11	14285900	A/C	-0.011	0.001	7.50E-14	-0.012	0.052	0.823
rs4788218	16	30055750	C/T	0.016	0.001	6.10E-32	-0.053	0.052	0.308
rs4788891	17	73391145	G/A	0.017	0.002	3.50E-23	0.088	0.078	0.26
rs4814656	20	17769540	A/G	-0.011	0.001	5.10E-18	0.049	0.051	0.331
rs4865956	5	54882505	A/T	-0.025	0.001	9.90E-69	-0.055	0.056	0.325
rs4870056	6	152162227	A/G	0.023	0.001	3.20E-68	-0.076	0.051	0.133
rs4870941	8	126498828	C/G	-0.018	0.002	2.00E-29	0.028	0.055	0.616
rs4886782	15	74228810	A/G	-0.023	0.001	2.10E-65	0.075	0.052	0.151
rs4887952	16	78347216	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.90E-15	0.046	0.061	0.448
rs4906203	14	102928991	T/C	-0.016	0.002	8.80E-26	-0.047	0.056	0.403
rs4908774	1	8770696	A/G	0.009	0.002	7.10E-09	0.017	0.064	0.797
rs4926633	1	54887567	C/T	-0.022	0.002	4.00E-21	0.073	0.088	0.404
rs4938330	11	116928514	G/C	-0.009	0.002	1.40E-08	0.047	0.057	0.406
rs4944961	11	74559481	T/C	0.008	0.001	3.80E-08	0.069	0.052	0.186
rs4969471	17	79977813	G/C	0.016	0.001	2.30E-28	-0.209	0.06	0.001
rs4974930	4	39238456	C/A	0.01	0.002	4.30E-11	-0.041	0.061	0.498
rs4974968	4	40172933	T/C	0.014	0.002	7.90E-19	-0.064	0.062	0.296
rs4982404	14	21539684	T/C	0.016	0.001	3.60E-33	-0.019	0.051	0.715
rs4986172	17	43216281	T/C	-0.021	0.001	1.80E-54	0.039	0.052	0.455
rs498685	18	13088673	C/T	-0.012	0.001	1.80E-20	0.056	0.05	0.266
rs505110	18	331506	A/G	0.011	0.001	5.10E-15	-0.011	0.052	0.837
rs508347	7	28212824	C/T	-0.035	0.001	6.70E-133	0.042	0.052	0.421
rs511987	11	125981569	C/T	-0.012	0.001	1.70E-17	0.036	0.052	0.49
rs519384	3	172168507	A/T	0.024	0.001	3.30E-62	0.062	0.056	0.269
rs527393	2	169709757	A/G	0.018	0.001	2.30E-42	0.037	0.05	0.458
rs52826764	2	20205541	T/C	-0.057	0.004	6.60E-51	0.049	0.183	0.789
rs55726184	14	24834971	A/G	-0.018	0.002	1.80E-17	0.034	0.085	0.687
rs55749333	17	7371932	T/C	-0.025	0.001	5.20E-74	-0.014	0.05	0.779
rs55778236	5	115022380	C/T	0.018	0.001	1.40E-33	0.031	0.054	0.561
rs55837722	10	94850473	C/G	0.016	0.002	6.60E-12	-0.033	0.079	0.674
rs55914260	18	29745501	T/C	0.011	0.002	1.40E-10	-0.081	0.069	0.239
rs55944294	6	18993264	A/C	0.013	0.002	9.80E-11	-0.049	0.104	0.637
rs55998444	2	128119846	C/T	0.008	0.001	6.70E-09	-0.057	0.057	0.314
rs56011514	4	109456614	G/A	0.013	0.001	7.50E-22	-0.001	0.052	0.984
rs56077950	4	122721412	T/C	0.017	0.001	3.20E-35	0.024	0.052	0.642
rs56128104	7	56071984	C/G	0.011	0.002	3.40E-13	-0.066	0.061	0.277
rs56400819	8	143925374	G/A	0.01	0.001	3.00E-14	0.021	0.052	0.688
rs56694848	9	691909	A/G	-0.01	0.002	3.60E-10	0.054	0.063	0.394
rs57240476	17	44195432	T/C	0.017	0.003	1.00E-09	0.141	0.142	0.319
rs57519358	2	218595240	G/A	-0.038	0.004	9.40E-20	0.168	0.164	0.306
rs578475	5	134354896	G/C	-0.022	0.001	1.80E-54	0.012	0.054	0.818
rs58087925	14	105983096	T/C	0.013	0.002	5.30E-16	0.04	0.056	0.478
rs591269	6	140227929	T/C	-0.008	0.001	2.10E-09	-0.038	0.05	0.456
rs59407416	10	23779283	T/G	0.011	0.001	7.00E-15	-0.007	0.056	0.902
rs595767	17	46957987	G/A	-0.021	0.001	3.20E-58	0.105	0.05	0.036
rs59735916	12	94385877	T/C	0.012	0.002	2.60E-12	-0.008	0.068	0.908
rs59951000	18	74975828	T/C	-0.021	0.003	6.80E-11	0.04	0.093	0.667

rs59985551	2	56106928	T/C	-0.05	0.002	1.00E-200	-0.03	0.06	0.622
rs6010778	20	61522019	C/T	0.01	0.001	5.30E-12	0.028	0.054	0.612
rs60131767	4	186703959	A/G	0.009	0.001	2.00E-11	-0.044	0.051	0.388
rs6020201	20	48634762	A/C	-0.013	0.002	7.40E-17	-0.018	0.06	0.765
rs6024734	20	54830299	T/C	0.011	0.002	2.80E-14	-0.063	0.06	0.292
rs60655524	8	67503514	A/G	-0.032	0.005	4.00E-11	0.251	0.087	0.004
rs6071822	20	38472158	A/G	0.011	0.002	2.30E-12	0.136	0.054	0.012
rs6082358	20	21230455	T/C	-0.013	0.001	6.70E-19	0.003	0.056	0.953
rs610798	1	32347703	C/G	0.023	0.002	9.00E-28	-0.103	0.084	0.22
rs6119945	20	31329256	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.70E-14	0.022	0.067	0.742
rs61635866	9	78555995	C/T	0.01	0.002	1.40E-10	-0.06	0.052	0.249
rs61729527	8	77761919	T/C	-0.023	0.003	1.90E-15	0.045	0.101	0.658
rs61732778	3	187443314	A/G	0.033	0.003	1.90E-39	-0.065	0.091	0.474
rs61776719	1	38461319	A/C	-0.016	0.001	4.50E-36	-0.049	0.052	0.35
rs61849823	10	53290991	C/T	0.017	0.002	2.40E-22	0.009	0.075	0.909
rs61919240	12	8831954	A/T	0.01	0.001	5.60E-14	0.012	0.055	0.825
rs61950149	13	21543502	C/T	-0.022	0.002	2.30E-25	-0.079	0.067	0.238
rs61987429	14	65606248	T/C	-0.017	0.001	1.00E-34	-0.047	0.052	0.367
rs62010237	15	66760891	A/T	-0.016	0.002	1.20E-10	0.003	0.092	0.978
rs62090043	17	1627704	C/T	-0.014	0.002	1.40E-19	-0.027	0.057	0.633
rs62274159	3	156885773	C/T	-0.015	0.002	4.90E-22	-0.004	0.066	0.956
rs62277396	3	156432088	G/C	-0.03	0.003	3.20E-19	0.018	0.132	0.889
rs62289317	4	7858189	T/G	0.009	0.001	1.60E-11	-0.004	0.052	0.947
rs62294340	3	169155476	A/G	0.009	0.001	7.00E-12	0.032	0.056	0.569
rs62337444	4	144524940	T/C	0.013	0.002	2.50E-13	-0.002	0.08	0.984
rs62338304	4	149719861	A/G	-0.008	0.001	2.90E-08	0.04	0.052	0.446
rs62358929	5	37785917	C/G	0.019	0.003	1.60E-14	-0.09	0.109	0.407
rs62370473	5	52767121	A/G	-0.012	0.002	8.10E-13	-0.017	0.059	0.78
rs62390617	6	1623627	C/G	0.016	0.002	6.00E-16	0.054	0.092	0.558
rs62396185	6	26180634	C/G	-0.041	0.001	2.50E-168	0.027	0.052	0.595
rs62423399	6	169030032	A/C	-0.009	0.002	1.90E-09	0.028	0.063	0.657
rs62473545	7	130636493	A/G	-0.015	0.002	1.30E-16	0.065	0.057	0.253
rs62501195	8	24041988	C/A	-0.029	0.002	1.50E-59	-0.019	0.06	0.755
rs62515437	8	57160328	T/G	0.031	0.002	8.40E-88	-0.021	0.055	0.702
rs62621197	19	8670147	T/C	-0.102	0.004	8.99E-178	0.205	0.18	0.255
rs6445804	3	56664852	G/A	-0.017	0.001	3.40E-38	0.039	0.05	0.431
rs6480350	10	70396822	C/T	0.009	0.001	3.60E-11	-0.002	0.051	0.966
rs6508350	18	22707449	T/C	0.01	0.001	4.50E-14	-0.057	0.051	0.256
rs6567160	18	57829135	C/T	0.021	0.002	1.00E-42	-0.013	0.065	0.841
rs6570503	6	142611580	T/C	-0.014	0.001	5.40E-27	0.059	0.05	0.245
rs6581626	12	65711378	G/A	-0.016	0.001	4.10E-35	0.013	0.05	0.803
rs659418	11	75284334	G/T	0.036	0.002	1.30E-81	0.006	0.065	0.926
rs6605522	6	169656531	G/A	0.013	0.002	1.60E-13	-0.047	0.062	0.451
rs66461782	1	71533287	T/A	0.011	0.001	8.60E-15	-0.03	0.052	0.57
rs6658835	1	218520995	G/A	0.015	0.001	4.30E-25	-0.044	0.055	0.418
rs66989638	2	106689736	A/G	0.018	0.002	6.00E-20	0.037	0.064	0.564
rs67012296	1	93900325	G/C	0.016	0.002	1.90E-11	0.101	0.084	0.226
rs670318	1	63727542	C/T	0.02	0.003	2.70E-11	-0.024	0.106	0.821
rs6739701	2	105132332	G/A	0.012	0.001	1.20E-20	-0.053	0.05	0.291
rs6744603	2	44476117	T/C	-0.017	0.002	8.40E-29	-0.035	0.053	0.508
rs67551338	12	3393100	T/C	0.021	0.003	2.20E-14	0.02	0.129	0.876
rs6756738	2	47008964	T/C	-0.017	0.001	1.00E-33	0.115	0.053	0.03
rs6761931	2	136150512	G/A	-0.017	0.002	1.40E-12	-0.065	0.092	0.483
rs6762578	3	128992047	A/G	0.028	0.002	6.10E-73	-0.01	0.067	0.881
rs6780813	3	33196428	C/T	-0.013	0.002	5.00E-11	0.067	0.063	0.287
rs6814272	4	83263637	A/G	-0.009	0.002	9.60E-09	-0.011	0.057	0.846
rs6822154	4	120761791	A/C	-0.01	0.001	3.90E-13	0.052	0.053	0.325
rs6824592	4	140059852	C/G	0.008	0.001	3.50E-08	-0.048	0.057	0.397
rs6828122	4	18006052	G/A	-0.056	0.002	1.00E-200	-0.061	0.086	0.476
rs683633	5	72400190	C/T	0.013	0.002	6.40E-13	-0.082	0.077	0.288
rs686112	17	47325717	C/T	0.012	0.001	5.50E-19	0.042	0.05	0.408
rs6863213	5	131575932	T/C	0.026	0.001	4.30E-86	0.068	0.054	0.212
rs686489	11	57659832	G/A	0.009	0.001	1.00E-11	0.004	0.054	0.94
rs6872083	5	39418421	G/A	-0.015	0.001	1.60E-26	0.031	0.053	0.565
rs6880702	5	158921895	A/G	-0.009	0.001	1.70E-10	-0.046	0.052	0.38

rs6900530	6	35280971	T/C	-0.068	0.004	1.30E-64	-0.135	0.236	0.567
rs6902285	6	52384286	C/A	0.01	0.001	1.30E-11	-0.12	0.058	0.037
rs6908258	6	155551005	T/C	-0.012	0.001	8.10E-19	-0.005	0.052	0.918
rs6923431	6	129824754	C/A	0.015	0.001	1.60E-24	0.007	0.053	0.902
rs6929227	6	47646468	C/T	0.008	0.001	2.80E-09	0.056	0.051	0.269
rs6938592	6	45097503	T/A	0.019	0.001	2.80E-39	0.008	0.056	0.891
rs6951990	7	120777717	A/C	-0.012	0.001	3.30E-19	-0.108	0.055	0.049
rs6962887	7	135045786	G/T	-0.015	0.001	3.60E-27	0.099	0.053	0.062
rs6964319	7	121633671	G/A	0.008	0.001	2.90E-10	-0.039	0.05	0.435
rs6981529	8	145040567	G/C	-0.019	0.001	6.80E-46	-0.043	0.051	0.405
rs6985031	8	130550637	C/T	-0.012	0.001	2.50E-19	-0.013	0.053	0.808
rs6987106	8	117552823	G/A	-0.013	0.002	3.80E-16	0.095	0.059	0.11
rs699371	14	74989433	C/T	0.021	0.001	7.30E-53	0.077	0.053	0.151
rs7010108	8	9130674	A/G	0.011	0.001	3.50E-15	0.121	0.069	0.079
rs7019613	9	101814852	C/T	-0.015	0.002	1.50E-15	-0.029	0.079	0.712
rs702101	5	171276393	A/G	0.026	0.001	1.40E-85	-0.115	0.051	0.025
rs7038554	9	139134981	G/A	0.021	0.001	4.10E-50	-0.014	0.054	0.792
rs703998	10	80912499	T/A	-0.018	0.001	8.60E-43	0.09	0.051	0.077
rs704660	11	30447998	T/C	0.014	0.001	2.30E-26	0.032	0.051	0.532
rs7071655	10	81234506	T/A	0.012	0.002	6.90E-11	0.044	0.061	0.469
rs7078243	10	94414263	C/A	-0.008	0.001	4.80E-10	-0.017	0.05	0.729
rs7087507	10	63745689	G/A	0.011	0.001	1.00E-14	0.056	0.056	0.322
rs709631	17	40555939	T/A	-0.008	0.001	3.40E-08	-0.017	0.053	0.747
rs7127911	11	128492549	T/G	0.009	0.001	2.50E-10	0.07	0.055	0.203
rs7129975	11	35483521	C/A	0.009	0.001	4.60E-10	0.015	0.052	0.766
rs7134283	12	24071748	A/G	-0.014	0.001	7.90E-22	0.058	0.056	0.304
rs71385734	16	2160503	G/T	-0.028	0.002	4.60E-56	-0.027	0.066	0.68
rs71393462	15	70022499	C/T	-0.033	0.002	1.50E-52	-0.141	0.103	0.172
rs71427097	2	97526963	T/C	-0.045	0.004	5.80E-30	0.079	0.146	0.587
rs71471298	10	105507145	T/C	0.021	0.002	6.60E-23	-0.03	0.077	0.695
rs7148360	14	76383138	A/G	-0.013	0.002	1.90E-17	0.084	0.061	0.167
rs716203	4	88836036	C/T	-0.007	0.001	2.60E-08	0.004	0.05	0.934
rs7194734	16	82199980	T/C	-0.016	0.002	3.30E-25	-0.107	0.066	0.106
rs7208285	17	76746325	A/G	-0.011	0.001	1.10E-15	-0.048	0.052	0.355
rs7223535	17	29211667	A/G	-0.041	0.001	2.50E-171	-0.036	0.056	0.518
rs723149	7	46577056	G/A	-0.017	0.001	9.10E-38	-0.016	0.05	0.75
rs7239515	18	41462359	C/G	0.009	0.001	2.70E-11	-0.004	0.052	0.945
rs7246328	19	18619057	C/T	-0.013	0.002	2.40E-12	0.2	0.068	0.003
rs7248294	19	46898234	C/T	0.017	0.003	2.40E-08	-0.132	0.089	0.137
rs7255241	19	37517289	A/C	-0.012	0.001	7.60E-18	-0.028	0.053	0.593
rs72649040	7	73028240	A/G	0.033	0.005	6.50E-12	0.43	0.188	0.022
rs72656010	8	57122215	C/T	-0.048	0.002	1.20E-134	0.021	0.076	0.782
rs72703414	4	184227430	G/A	-0.029	0.003	1.50E-27	-0.056	0.133	0.672
rs72720395	14	64709091	T/C	-0.01	0.002	1.00E-11	-0.065	0.06	0.281
rs72721182	1	172258325	C/T	0.035	0.002	3.30E-105	-0.072	0.063	0.253
rs72755233	15	100692953	A/G	-0.062	0.002	1.20E-195	-0.018	0.079	0.817
rs72759895	1	243664098	C/G	0.024	0.003	1.00E-17	-0.071	0.149	0.636
rs72776486	5	77515056	A/C	-0.017	0.002	9.50E-30	-0.074	0.065	0.254
rs72843872	2	85820027	G/A	0.013	0.001	5.80E-20	0.078	0.059	0.187
rs72887152	2	156604025	A/T	0.015	0.002	5.50E-17	-0.058	0.071	0.414
rs72904749	1	51367420	T/C	0.033	0.002	2.70E-47	0.024	0.109	0.827
rs72976986	19	4050424	A/G	0.016	0.002	5.70E-21	0.001	0.069	0.987
rs7299310	12	66121262	C/T	0.016	0.002	1.90E-16	0.041	0.059	0.481
rs73013411	6	164126233	A/C	0.02	0.002	5.00E-25	-0.094	0.091	0.306
rs7305516	12	102382052	G/A	-0.019	0.001	1.50E-46	-0.005	0.051	0.93
rs7306710	12	66376091	C/T	-0.042	0.001	1.00E-200	-0.012	0.05	0.81
rs73074166	20	5112714	A/T	-0.019	0.002	1.30E-17	0.213	0.111	0.055
rs7311238	12	54020492	A/G	-0.014	0.002	1.20E-15	0.004	0.062	0.95
rs73125628	20	20066701	T/C	-0.012	0.001	1.20E-15	0.027	0.052	0.611
rs73155600	4	56915061	A/C	-0.009	0.001	1.50E-10	-0.043	0.06	0.473
rs731646	3	12857823	T/C	-0.008	0.001	5.30E-09	-0.036	0.05	0.475
rs7318247	13	96814456	A/G	-0.012	0.002	4.40E-10	0.167	0.083	0.045
rs7319045	13	92024574	G/A	-0.02	0.001	1.40E-49	-0.089	0.05	0.076
rs73234767	3	142634502	T/C	-0.01	0.002	1.30E-08	0.051	0.059	0.392
rs73453871	15	89261671	A/G	0.013	0.002	7.80E-13	0.034	0.071	0.63

rs73471549	7	139910746	A/G	-0.01	0.001	2.50E-11	-0.002	0.061	0.968
rs734764	9	90852624	C/G	-0.019	0.002	3.80E-33	0.067	0.063	0.285
rs737380	21	38077468	G/A	0.009	0.002	2.60E-10	0.007	0.06	0.902
rs7430034	3	134342127	T/C	0.013	0.001	1.50E-22	0.045	0.056	0.416
rs743282	8	37336539	T/C	0.01	0.002	8.10E-09	0.027	0.068	0.694
rs74461473	3	50250747	T/C	-0.02	0.002	8.60E-22	0.071	0.106	0.5
rs74564500	2	183786420	A/C	0.016	0.002	2.70E-11	0.012	0.119	0.918
rs745749	5	179715803	G/A	-0.012	0.001	7.80E-19	0.034	0.052	0.512
rs7469817	9	118296829	C/G	0.015	0.001	2.60E-24	-0.081	0.057	0.159
rs75076724	14	104014690	C/T	0.021	0.002	6.90E-29	-0.058	0.067	0.39
rs7518201	1	203773096	C/A	0.014	0.002	7.10E-14	-0.005	0.061	0.931
rs7539511	1	2862320	T/G	0.008	0.001	3.70E-08	-0.021	0.051	0.677
rs75396144	6	56890083	C/T	-0.011	0.002	1.60E-09	-0.119	0.065	0.065
rs754532	11	65747057	A/G	0.011	0.001	5.80E-14	0.043	0.052	0.407
rs7575825	2	199176823	T/C	-0.01	0.002	7.20E-09	-0.015	0.075	0.844
rs757834	7	139717200	C/T	0.015	0.002	3.20E-18	0.003	0.066	0.965
rs7585767	2	70338344	G/A	-0.01	0.001	1.50E-15	0.025	0.052	0.635
rs7593100	2	183694499	T/C	0.014	0.002	2.20E-09	0.12	0.128	0.349
rs7594625	2	218293564	G/T	-0.019	0.001	1.50E-44	0.036	0.051	0.475
rs7595271	2	105873193	A/G	-0.013	0.002	5.70E-11	-0.015	0.073	0.839
rs76147573	2	12174147	G/A	0.012	0.002	6.30E-09	-0.029	0.084	0.73
rs76152268	2	216303813	C/T	-0.047	0.006	7.50E-18	0.053	0.129	0.683
rs7621604	3	61557718	G/A	-0.019	0.001	7.90E-46	-0.019	0.05	0.706
rs7627625	3	168899725	C/G	0.02	0.003	1.10E-10	-0.028	0.147	0.85
rs76292187	19	42754403	A/G	-0.025	0.003	3.20E-21	0.068	0.129	0.599
rs76325149	7	100389590	T/C	-0.015	0.003	4.70E-08	-0.083	0.087	0.342
rs7632937	3	14169079	C/T	-0.024	0.003	2.00E-12	0.151	0.097	0.118
rs76364830	8	13372120	A/G	-0.031	0.003	2.50E-30	0.073	0.137	0.593
rs7636734	3	37746851	C/T	0.008	0.001	1.50E-10	-0.042	0.05	0.405
rs7641322	3	145868489	T/G	-0.008	0.001	1.50E-10	0.018	0.051	0.722
rs7651940	3	169256240	T/C	-0.011	0.001	1.50E-17	-0.002	0.05	0.966
rs7652117	3	58008093	C/T	-0.014	0.001	3.60E-25	0.063	0.051	0.218
rs76602912	20	57459868	C/T	-0.041	0.004	1.40E-21	0.022	0.168	0.898
rs768023	6	108876002	A/G	0.016	0.001	8.30E-33	-0.009	0.051	0.858
rs7681267	4	87073599	C/T	0.042	0.005	5.40E-16	0.06	0.505	0.905
rs76887969	9	99224962	G/C	0.03	0.002	2.90E-35	-0.063	0.112	0.575
rs7689420	4	145568352	C/T	0.06	0.002	1.00E-200	-0.175	0.067	0.01
rs76895963	12	4384844	G/T	0.125	0.005	1.80E-134	-0.334	0.149	0.025
rs7697556	4	73515313	C/T	-0.023	0.001	7.40E-72	0.033	0.05	0.506
rs77124518	15	38362264	C/T	0.016	0.002	3.10E-14	0.082	0.098	0.402
rs77303550	16	72079657	T/C	0.011	0.002	9.50E-12	0.019	0.064	0.766
rs77330849	12	133374905	T/C	0.013	0.002	5.40E-12	0.051	0.092	0.58
rs7753558	6	117523471	A/C	0.019	0.001	4.00E-44	0.114	0.054	0.035
rs77672559	17	28135103	T/A	-0.021	0.002	9.20E-24	0.041	0.074	0.584
rs778407	1	56704424	T/G	0.014	0.002	5.30E-19	0.091	0.061	0.136
rs7794796	7	150540196	T/C	0.02	0.001	9.10E-46	0.046	0.052	0.38
rs78051210	6	131379491	C/T	0.031	0.002	6.30E-36	0.028	0.121	0.82
rs7814941	8	130718859	G/A	-0.036	0.002	4.00E-106	0.115	0.066	0.081
rs7818782	8	96420039	T/C	-0.012	0.002	4.90E-11	0.083	0.076	0.273
rs78249916	4	12740962	T/C	0.026	0.003	4.90E-20	-0.061	0.122	0.618
rs78264848	5	121191166	A/G	0.019	0.003	6.10E-09	-0.064	0.088	0.465
rs78306761	20	7385054	A/G	-0.01	0.002	1.10E-08	-0.047	0.061	0.444
rs78428113	17	79115880	T/C	0.012	0.002	1.10E-10	-0.101	0.079	0.204
rs7847753	9	4163904	C/T	0.008	0.001	1.10E-08	-0.02	0.054	0.71
rs7861226	9	123351121	A/C	0.01	0.001	9.20E-13	-0.01	0.059	0.868
rs78805413	11	2131018	A/G	-0.032	0.003	2.40E-29	0.282	0.11	0.01
rs78817479	9	17040371	A/C	-0.02	0.002	1.30E-17	-0.16	0.116	0.169
rs7911018	10	131348554	T/C	0.01	0.001	5.60E-15	0.094	0.052	0.068
rs7916821	10	69933969	A/G	0.017	0.001	9.30E-40	-0.048	0.05	0.344
rs7928703	11	29080664	G/T	-0.009	0.001	7.90E-11	-0.025	0.05	0.622
rs7943920	11	12695614	G/A	0.016	0.001	5.40E-33	0.067	0.051	0.184
rs79449299	4	38615469	T/C	-0.017	0.002	7.90E-17	-0.105	0.077	0.175
rs7946010	11	17176057	A/G	-0.012	0.001	8.50E-19	0.041	0.05	0.416
rs7952436	11	67024534	T/C	-0.074	0.002	1.00E-200	-0.066	0.114	0.56
rs7957659	12	50638810	C/T	-0.011	0.001	8.70E-18	-0.03	0.051	0.554

rs79584445	14	88893418	C/T	-0.034	0.006	2.50E-09	0.142	0.16	0.373
rs79621178	5	108091191	C/G	0.031	0.002	6.70E-39	0.027	0.095	0.772
rs7964039	12	39736740	T/C	0.014	0.003	2.50E-08	0.046	0.112	0.679
rs7971877	12	58287630	G/T	-0.013	0.001	3.40E-21	-0.008	0.051	0.88
rs79728014	11	46062245	G/A	0.021	0.002	1.60E-29	-0.04	0.072	0.573
rs79747671	12	103140344	T/C	-0.025	0.002	1.60E-33	0.013	0.075	0.865
rs79749090	17	27417209	G/A	0.016	0.003	2.60E-10	0.007	0.111	0.951
rs7976738	12	91495838	C/T	-0.01	0.002	1.10E-08	-0.051	0.085	0.548
rs7978217	12	20630869	G/T	0.008	0.001	1.20E-09	-0.022	0.05	0.67
rs798490	7	2801542	A/G	-0.042	0.001	3.00E-184	0.049	0.052	0.345
rs7987131	13	99593241	A/G	-0.008	0.001	1.30E-08	-0.056	0.057	0.319
rs8016947	14	35832666	G/T	0.008	0.001	2.90E-09	-0.014	0.051	0.782
rs8029053	15	89450087	T/C	-0.014	0.001	8.80E-23	0.005	0.059	0.94
rs8033211	15	63061887	G/C	0.008	0.001	4.10E-09	0.035	0.058	0.544
rs803804	13	71599302	T/C	0.008	0.001	5.90E-09	-0.088	0.054	0.102
rs8094658	18	2761338	G/A	0.008	0.001	1.10E-08	0.024	0.052	0.644
rs811133	14	54647436	C/T	0.009	0.002	2.10E-08	0.03	0.058	0.609
rs822530	7	148631555	T/A	0.034	0.002	2.00E-97	-0.084	0.067	0.212
rs823118	1	205723572	T/C	-0.015	0.001	4.00E-31	-0.127	0.051	0.013
rs833149	2	183223013	C/T	-0.008	0.001	6.40E-09	0.011	0.053	0.842
rs835118	5	14956699	A/G	0.009	0.001	5.40E-10	-0.016	0.057	0.78
rs852946	6	72165420	A/G	0.009	0.001	3.20E-12	0.012	0.052	0.822
rs855286	12	102946454	C/T	-0.022	0.002	4.00E-22	-0.118	0.089	0.187
rs876122	6	6886297	G/A	0.025	0.002	7.80E-37	0.058	0.069	0.401
rs883668	3	114554021	G/A	-0.025	0.003	1.00E-19	0.045	0.153	0.77
rs893900	15	67014528	T/C	-0.016	0.001	5.20E-34	-0.028	0.05	0.585
rs927578	13	28075022	T/G	0.011	0.002	9.80E-09	0.103	0.066	0.116
rs9300607	13	101223459	C/A	-0.009	0.001	9.90E-11	0.003	0.05	0.956
rs933561	16	49874676	G/A	-0.012	0.001	5.90E-18	-0.011	0.057	0.844
rs9345893	6	67512311	T/G	-0.008	0.001	1.00E-08	-0.003	0.057	0.953
rs9350850	6	81050236	C/T	0.04	0.002	3.10E-63	-0.057	0.079	0.469
rs9365939	6	166336825	G/A	-0.012	0.001	1.30E-19	-0.008	0.052	0.872
rs9379084	6	7231843	A/G	-0.032	0.002	1.00E-51	-0.026	0.08	0.747
rs9391254	6	105377347	T/C	0.036	0.001	9.71E-146	0.028	0.054	0.608
rs941346	7	70254674	T/G	-0.008	0.001	4.50E-09	-0.105	0.052	0.044
rs9435731	1	17306029	A/C	0.029	0.001	1.30E-107	0.008	0.05	0.871
rs9442571	1	9349611	A/T	0.025	0.002	3.70E-39	0.024	0.064	0.711
rs9443189	6	76495882	G/A	-0.014	0.002	3.20E-14	-0.085	0.07	0.226
rs9487084	6	109717088	G/T	-0.017	0.001	5.90E-40	-0.026	0.05	0.607
rs9496369	6	142724918	T/C	-0.04	0.001	8.49E-168	0.003	0.057	0.96
rs9535015	13	48904509	A/C	-0.012	0.001	4.00E-15	0.002	0.055	0.965
rs9543310	13	73859958	A/G	0.009	0.001	2.30E-09	0.007	0.061	0.909
rs9545588	13	81615536	A/G	-0.009	0.001	4.50E-10	0.036	0.054	0.51
rs9574556	13	80646366	C/G	0.012	0.002	1.30E-12	-0.014	0.072	0.841
rs9575875	13	85931285	G/A	0.01	0.001	6.40E-14	-0.04	0.053	0.449
rs9576006	13	36944732	A/G	-0.008	0.001	1.50E-08	0.028	0.059	0.638
rs9576134	13	37481694	G/C	0.009	0.002	2.60E-09	-0.016	0.067	0.816
rs9590405	13	114999838	G/A	-0.018	0.002	4.30E-32	0.055	0.059	0.348
rs960225	11	1952089	A/C	0.016	0.002	2.70E-14	0.024	0.086	0.782
rs9614670	22	45838817	T/C	0.017	0.002	8.10E-25	-0.038	0.066	0.567
rs9634212	12	93993266	A/C	0.039	0.002	2.60E-136	0.055	0.058	0.34
rs966541	12	29491528	G/A	0.015	0.001	2.60E-24	-0.008	0.055	0.878
rs9696477	9	136399315	T/C	-0.011	0.002	8.20E-11	-0.078	0.054	0.15
rs9747062	17	8023057	C/A	0.014	0.001	6.50E-25	0.001	0.052	0.979
rs9809116	3	72397279	G/A	-0.024	0.001	2.90E-75	0.035	0.053	0.509
rs9824877	3	98896242	A/G	-0.01	0.002	1.50E-10	0.005	0.06	0.936
rs9826470	3	38019428	T/C	0.017	0.002	2.40E-28	-0.061	0.068	0.364
rs9830029	3	33262129	A/G	0.01	0.001	7.50E-14	0.084	0.05	0.095
rs985344	3	67347767	A/G	-0.019	0.002	1.90E-18	-0.032	0.099	0.75
rs9875575	3	88299112	G/A	0.009	0.002	1.50E-08	-0.054	0.055	0.32
rs9880232	3	185360578	A/C	0.012	0.001	4.90E-16	-0.009	0.057	0.874
rs9894127	17	59625479	A/G	0.013	0.001	5.70E-20	-0.052	0.059	0.381
rs9894946	17	7571080	G/A	0.012	0.002	3.70E-11	0.011	0.07	0.881
rs9941239	16	84987947	G/A	-0.015	0.002	6.70E-22	0.048	0.061	0.428